

MAKSIMAL NOCHIZIQLI IMPULSLI DIFFERENSIAL TENGLAMALAR

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Annotatsiya. *Impuls ta’sirli va maksimumlarga ega oddiy differensial tenglamalar sistemasi uchun nolokal chegaraviy masala o‘rganildi. Chegaraviy masala integral shart bilan beriladi. Ketma-ket yaqinlashish usuli bilan birgalikda qo‘llaniladi. Chegaraviy masala yechimining mavjudligi va yagonaligi isbotlangan.*

Kalit so‘zlar: *impulslil differensial tenglamalar, nolokal chegaraviy shart, ketma-ket yaqinlashishlar, yechimning mavjudligi va yagonaligi, yechimning uzluksiz bog‘liqligi.*

Аннотация. *Исследована нелокальная краевая задача для системы обыкновенных дифференциальных уравнений с импульсными эффектами и максимумами. Краевая задача задается интегральным условием. Используется совместно с методом последовательных приближений. Доказано существование и единственность решения краевой задачи.*

Ключевые слова: *дифференциальные уравнения импульса, нелокальные граничные условия, последовательные приближения, существование и единственность решения, непрерывная зависимость решения.*

Annotation. *A nonlocal boundary value problem for a system of ordinary differential equations with impulse effects and maxima is studied. The boundary value problem is given by the integral condition. Used in conjunction with the method of successive approximations. The existence and uniqueness of a solution to the boundary value problem is proven.*

Key words: *differential equations of momentum, nonlocal boundary conditions, successive approximations, existence and uniqueness of a solution, continuous dependence of the solution.*

Quyidagi differensial tenglamalar sistemasi

$$x'(t) = f\left(t, x(t), \max\left\{x(\tau) \mid \tau \in [h_1; h_2]\right\}\right), \quad t \in [0, T], \quad t \neq t_i, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, p, \quad (1)$$

chiziqli bo‘lmagan chegaraviy shart bilan

$$Ax(0) + \int_0^T K(t)x(t)dt = B \quad (2)$$

va

$$x(t_i^+) - x(t_i^-) = I_i(x(t_i)), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, p, \quad (3)$$

impulsi ta'sir bilan berilgan bo'lsin, bu yerda

$$0 = t_0 < t_1 < \dots < t_p < t_{p+1} = T, A \in R^{n \times n}, K(t) \in R^{n \times n} \text{ matritsa va}$$

$$\det Q \neq 0, Q = A + \int_0^T K(t) dt, f : [0, T] \times R^n \rightarrow R^n, I_i : R^n \rightarrow R^n \text{ berilgan funksiyalar;}$$

$$0 < h_1 < h_2 < t, h_j = h_j(t, x(t)), j = 1, 2, x(t_i^+) = \lim_{h \rightarrow 0^+} x(t_i + h), x(t_i^-) = \lim_{h \rightarrow 0^-} x(t_i - h)$$

mos ravishda $x(t)$ funksiyaning $t = t_i$ nuqtadagi o'ng va chap tomonli limitlari.

Integral tenglamaga keltirish.

Quyida ba'zi belgilashlardan foydalanamiz. $C([0, T], R^n)$ fazo $x(t)$ uzluksiz vektor funksiyalardan tashkil topgan Banax fazosini bildiradi. $[0, T]$ segmentda aniqlangan uzluksiz vektor funksiyalar uchun norma quyidagicha kiritiladi:

$$\|x\| = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n \max_{[0, T]} |x_j(t)|}.$$

$PC([0, T], R^n)$ orqali quyidagi chiziqli fazoni belgilaymiz:

$$PC([0, T], R^n) = \left\{ x : [0, T] \rightarrow R^n; x(t) \in C((t_i, t_{i+1}], R^n), i = 1, \dots, p \right\},$$

bu yerda $x(t_i^+)$ va $x(t_i^-)$ ($i = 0, 1, \dots, p$) lar mavjud va ular chegaralangan; $x(t_i^-) = x(t_i)$.

Ko'rinib turibdiki, $PC([0, T], R^n)$ chiziqli Banax fazosida norma quyidagicha kiritiladi:

$$\|x\|_{PC} = \max \left\{ \|x\|_{C((t_i, t_{i+1}])}, i = 1, 2, \dots, p \right\}.$$

$x(t) \in PC([0, T], R^n)$ funksiya barcha $t \in [0, T], t \neq t_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, p$ uchun (1) differensial tenglamani qanoatlantiradi. Shuningdek, ushbu funksiya (2) nolokal integral shartni va $t = t_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, p, 0 < t_1 < t_2 < \dots < t_p < T$ lar uchun (3) chegaraviy shartni qanoatlantiradi.

Quyidagicha belgilash kiritamiz:

$$G(t) = \begin{cases} Q^{-1} \left(A + \int_0^t K(s) ds \right), & 0 \leq s \leq t, \\ -Q^{-1} \int_t^T K(s) ds, & t < s \leq T. \end{cases}$$

$x(t) \in PC([0, T], R^n)$ funksiya (1)-(3) masalaning yechimi bo‘ladi. U holda (1) tenglamani $t \in (0, t_{i+1}]$, intervalda integrallash orqali quyidagi tenglikka ega bo‘lamiz:

$$\int_0^t f(s, x(s), \cdot) ds = \int_0^t x'(s) ds = [x(t_1) - x(0^+)] + [x(t_2) - x(t_1^+)] + \dots + [x(t) - x(t_i^+)] = -x(0) - [x(t_1^+) - x(t_1)] - [x(t_2^+) - x(t_2)] - \dots - [x(t_i^+) - x(t_i)] + x(t).$$

Oxirgi tenglikda (2) integral shartni hisobga olib quyidagi tenglikka ega bo‘lamiz:

$$x(t) = x(0) + \int_0^t f(s, x(s), \cdot) ds + \sum_{0 < t_i < t} I_i(x(t_i)). \quad (4)$$

(4) tenglikdagi berilgan $x(t) \in PC([0, T], R^n)$ funksiya (2) chegaraviy shartni qanoatlantiradi:

$$\left[A + \int_0^T K(t) dt \right] x(0) = B - \int_0^T K(t) \int_0^t f(s, x(s), \cdot) ds dt - \int_0^T K(t) \sum_{0 < t_i < t} I_i(x(t_i)) dt. \quad (5)$$

$\det Q \neq 0$ ni hisobga olsak, (5) tenglikdan quyidagiga ega bo‘lamiz:

$$x(0) = Q^{-1} \left[B - \int_0^T K(t) \int_0^t f(s, x(s), \cdot) ds dt - \int_0^T K(t) \sum_{0 < t_i < t} I_i(x(t_i)) dt \right]. \quad (6)$$

(6) tenglikni (4) dagi o‘rniga almashtirib, quyidagi tenglikni hosil qilamiz:

$$x(t) = Q^{-1} \left[B - \int_0^T K(t) \int_0^t f(s, x(s), \cdot) ds dt - \int_0^T K(t) \sum_{0 < t_i < t} dt \right] + \int_0^t f(s, x(s), \cdot) ds + \sum_{0 < t_i < t} I_i(x(t_i)). \quad (7)$$

Quyidagi

$$\int_0^T K(t) \int_0^t f(s, x(s), \cdot) ds dt = \int_0^T \int_0^T K(s) ds f(t, x(t), \cdot) d(t),$$

$$\int_0^T K(t) \sum_{0 < t_i < t} I_i(x(t_i)) dt = \sum_{0 < t_i < T} \int_{t_i}^T K(t) dt I_i(x(t_i)),$$

tengliklarni hisobga olib, (7) tenglikni quyidagicha yozamiz:

$$x(t) = Q^{-1} B - Q^{-1} \int_0^T \int_0^T K(s) ds f(t, x(t), \cdot) dt - Q^{-1} \sum_{0 < t_i < t} \int_{t_i}^T K(t) dt I_i(x(t_i)) + \int_0^t f(s, x(s), \cdot) ds + \sum_{0 < t_i < t} I_i(x(t_i)). \quad (8)$$

Endi (8) tenglikni biroz soddalashtiraylik. U holda quyidagi tengliklarni hosil qilamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^t f(s, x(s), \cdot) ds - Q^{-1} \int_0^T \int_t^T K(s) ds f(t, x(t), \cdot) d(t) = \\ & = Q^{-1} \int_0^t \left(A + \int_0^\theta K(s) ds \right) f(\theta, x(\theta), \cdot) d\theta - Q^{-1} \int_0^T \int_t^T K(s) ds f(\theta, x(\theta), \cdot) d\theta; \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{0 < t_i < t} I_i(x(t_i)) - Q^{-1} \sum_{0 < t_i < T} \int_{t_i}^T K(t) dt I_i(x(t_i)) = \\ & = Q^{-1} \sum_{0 < t_i < t} \left(A + \int_0^{t_i} K(t) dt \right) I_i(x(t_i)) - \sum_{t < t_{i+1} < T} Q^{-1} \int_{t_i}^T K(t) dt I_i(x(t_i)). \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

(9) va (10) tengliklarni hisobga olib, (8) tenglamani quyidagicha yozamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} x(t) = J(t; x) \equiv & Q^{-1} B + \\ & + \int_0^T G(s) f\left(s, x(s), \max\{x(\tau) \mid \tau \in [h_1; h_2]\}\right) ds + \sum_{0 < t_i < t} G(t_i) I_i(x(t_i)) \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

bu yerda $t \in (t_i, t_{i+1}]$, $i = 0, 1, \dots, p$, $h_j = h_j(t, x(t))$, $j = 1, 2$.

(11) integral tenglama (1)-(3) masalani qanoatlantirishini tekshirish qiyin emas.

Yechimni yagonaligi.

Teorema. Aytaylik, quyidagi shartlar bajarilsin:

1). Barcha $t \in [0, T]$, $x, y \in R^n$ uchun

$$|f(t, x_1, y_1) - f(t, x_2, y_2)| \leq M_1(t) |x_1 - x_2| + M_2(t) |y_1 - y_2|;$$

2). Barcha $t \in [0, T]$, $x \in R^n$ uchun

$$|h_j(t, x_1) - h_j(t, x_2)| \leq M_{3j}(t) |x_1 - x_2|, \quad j = 1, 2;$$

3). Barcha $x, y \in R^n$, $i = 0, 1, \dots, p$ uchun

$$|I_i(x_1) - I_i(x_2)| \leq m_i |x_1 - x_2|;$$

4). $\rho = S_1 + S_2 < 1$, bu yerda

$$S_1 = \int_0^T |G(s)| \cdot \left[M_1(s) + M_2(s) \left(1 + M_f(M_{31}(s) + M_{32}(s)) \right) \right] ds,$$

$$S_2 = \sum_{i=1}^p |G(t_i)| \cdot m_i.$$

U holda (1)-(3) nolokal chegaraviy masala yagona $x(t) \in PC([0, T], R^n)$ yechimga ega. Ushbu yechimni quyidagi iteratsiya usulidan topish mumkin:

$$\begin{cases} x^k(t) = J(t; x^{k-1}), k = 1, 2, 3, \dots \\ x^0(t) = Q^{-1}B, t \in (t_i, t_{i+1}), i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, p. \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

Bundan tashqari, ushbu yechim uchun quyidagi tengsizlik o‘rinli:

$$\|x_1(t) - x_2(t)\|_{PC} \leq (1 - \rho)^{-1} \|Q^{-1}\| \cdot \|B_1 - B_2\|.$$

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